

Policy Brief – Delivering access to energy in Ethiopia: governance, efficiency and implementation

In this policy brief, we provide insights drawn from the [Energy system development pathways for Ethiopia \(PATHWAYS\) Project](#), based on modelling of the Ethiopian energy system, [different future energy narratives](#), residential energy use analysis, and repeated engagement with local and international energy experts.

Expanding electricity access to Ethiopia's growing population has historically been slow with connections improving by 1.2% per annum over the past 25 years. Currently, around 60 million people still lack access – the majority located in rural, often remote areas of the country. While paradoxically large shares of this population are within 10km of existing grid infrastructure, only 34% of rural households are connected.

Headline Messages

- Ethiopia has ambitious targets for national electrification that imply a strong reliance on the use of mini- and off-grid technologies.
- Our scenarios show that mini-grids will play a crucial role to 2050 and beyond serving between 3 and 40 million people in remote areas.
- While strong progress in recent years has established a governance framework that follows best international practice in support of off-grid projects, an implementation gap remains with specific barriers to its effective application.
- Closing this gap is crucial and will require streamlined processes, stronger devolved institutions, and an approach that involves multi-stakeholder collaboration.
- Our analysis of key examples in the residential sector suggest that direct energy savings could be double those expected by the EEA, while indirect shifts in power investment could reach 25GW by 2065.

National targets for electrification under existing government policy are ambitious. The National Electrification Plan expects the country to roll out universal access to electricity by 2025 from a recent baseline of 44% in 2018. This will rely on the national grid for 65% of the population. Short term, the remainder are expected to rely on off- and mini-grid technologies until these can be integrated into an expanding grid.

Mini-grid systems will be a strong enabler of future electrification in Ethiopia. Reaching the national targets outlined above implies seeing significant growth in the size of Ethiopia's energy system. Our analysis suggests that centralised power supply will increase between 6 and 60-fold by 2050. This suggests a build rate of up to 5GW per annum.

These systems will feed the national grid, and the scenarios run under the Pathways project highlight stark differences in electrification patterns – i.e. what technology is used at which locations – as a function of how demand evolves. This in turn

is particularly sensitive to how fast newly connected settlements move from lower to higher Tiers of electrification.

There is an important link between increased cost and increases in end use service as systems are extended on a cost optimal basis. [Our previous policy brief](#) highlighted that forced grid expansion is not cost optimal. Allowing mini-grid and off-grid systems to play a larger transition role in areas where demand is developing more slowly could lower financial pressure in the near term, reducing the overall cost of electrification by up to 40%.

In this context, our results show that both off-grid PV and mini-grid systems have a role to play in the provision of cost-effective power. They also show that they are an important option to future proof the energy system and improve energy security.

Under most scenarios, mini-grid systems can be expected to provide electricity to between 3 and 4 million people by 2050. Under our New Policies scenario, this translates to serving approximately 1.2 million households in the same timeframe. In alternative outlooks, where either access to electricity is prioritized for other sectors of the economy, or where progress is slow ('big business' and 'slow down' scenarios), mini-grids are seen to still be providing electricity to between 24 and 40 million people between 2040 and 2070.

Mini-grid systems will serve as rungs up the energy ladder in the medium term. As Ethiopia continues to target middle-income country status, with a need for economic recovery to pick up to achieve their mid-2020 target, remote populations will gradually increase their energy use, moving up the Tiers of electrification. Describing this shift, our scenarios show that standalone PV systems are useful for achieving energy access, but that goals of servicing modern energy needs with high capacity electricity will require mini-grids and, ultimately, central grids. Unexplored however is the role mini-grids can play to support areas too remote for grid access, either as transitional options or by displacing the need for the grid altogether.

Where development implies higher levels of demand, mini-grid systems will be incorporated into the grid as it expands, reducing the overall system cost. We note that this may happen before the economic lifetime of all assets involved in the mini-grid system have lapsed.

Finally, there is always a role for PV based off-grid and mini-grid systems to serve last mile electrification in very remote locations where grid electrification is simply too expensive. This is particularly the case in the south-eastern part of the country.

Significant progress in establishing regulations supportive of mini-grids has been seen in recent years in Ethiopia. A review and classification of renewable mini-grid policy and regulatory design features was undertaken for the years 2017 and 2021. The research developed a systematic framework based on key characteristics of policies found across 20 ‘high-impact’ countries. These are countries in sub-Saharan Africa and Asia which together account for nearly 80% of the global electricity access deficit. Ethiopia is one of these countries.

Under this lens, it is apparent that steps have been taken to plug the governance gaps highlighted in 2017. These include: policy planning for: locational mini-grid demarcations; regulatory measures applying to licensing, cost-reflective tariffs and risk; supporting mechanisms for funding and technical assistance through active donor organisation engagement; and, review of the environmental impacts of project development.

This policy framework gives reassurance that Ethiopia is well placed to provide what modelling results suggest is necessary to meet both national targets and people’s needs.

Our investigation suggests a significant implementation gap remains, which separates “on paper” adequacy from “on the ground” advances. While Ethiopia has national electrification targets for 2025 and beyond, and the apparent policy framework to support their implementation, interviews revealed that the country is seen as highly unlikely to meet these targets.

Ethiopia is invested in its mini-grid strategy, as demonstrated by two planned pilot projects for 12 and 25 solar mini-grids in the tender and commissioning phases respectively. However, interviews with national and international experts suggested that progress in Ethiopia’s mini-grid sector remained limited.

Through structured discussions, experts, researchers and practitioners, suggested that there is a knowledge and implementation gap that separates the strong regulatory framework from on the ground application to mini-grid projects. Procedures for integrating infrastructure into the grid when it arrives, and compensating owners, remain unclear. Institutional structures suggested to date do not include links to local government and governance remains top-down throughout the power sector, generating additional

bureaucracies. Furthermore, licensing procedures remain lengthy and complex, introducing additional risk for developers.

Overall, our research highlights that streamlined processes and strengthened institutions could provide the support needed to close this gap. Fostering multi-stakeholder collaboration, creating an implementation process that builds on experiences and lessons learned from a growing range of off-grid projects in the country would bring necessary learnings back into national frameworks.

Resolving these implementation gaps can save significant amounts of public funding. Taking a closer look at a residential example, simulation analysis complements this governance work by highlighting the potential benefits of successful regulations.

Proposed by the EEA, the implementation of Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) is under development in Ethiopia. They are anticipated to regulate electric appliances that serve residential energy use, including injera baking, cooking and lighting. Our research suggests that savings involved can be substantial. If full implementation is achieved by 2030 this could reduce energy use by as much as 30% in the sector between 2017 and 2065. Going further, this reduces the power system size by up to 25GW by 2065. A strong portion of this avoided investment is in fossil fuel capacity with fossil gas systems representing 9GW of this total saving.

Looking at multiple futures, our results highlight that energy saving from planned electric injera mitad MEPS sit at the lower end of the range of potential savings, but also that these could be doubled vs. current estimates by the EEA.

Our exploration showed marginal gains in added savings when shifting full implementation of MEPS deadlines from 2030 to 2040, suggesting that a robust MEPS programme – enabled by effective governance – is to be prioritised over a fast-tracked timetable. The importance of this recommendation is noted by the current situation of incandescent lightbulbs in the country, which are still available and in use notwithstanding regulation to ban them. Thus, highlighting the need to prioritise effective governance and implementation of chosen regulations.

Methods the Pathways project developed original analysis using different tools and approaches, the results of which are combined to present this policy note. Plausible scenarios for electrification were co-developed with local stakeholders and modelled using i) a whole system energy optimization model (OSeMOSYS) and ii) a GIS based electrification optimization model (OnSSET). Further reading: [Pappis et al. 2020](#) and [Tomei et al. 2020](#). A longitudinal analysis of 20 “high-impact” countries for their progress on regulatory practices in relation to building, and operating mini-grid solutions for electrification. This included both direct and secondary references reporting mini-grid policies and regulations, and was complemented by semi-structured expert interviews conducted with local experts and academics to provide a deeper understanding of Ethiopia’s mini-grid environment. It to establishes eight policy and regulatory domains within the overarching categories of ‘policy and planning’, ‘regulatory measures’ and ‘supporting measures’, which were selected to capture a broader range of measures than any single framework. The domains were applied as a top-down analytical framework to classify and characterise relevant policy and regulation for each country using qualitative content analysis Finally, a LEAP model of the Ethiopian Residential sector was developed to assess i) assess energy demand from a bottom up perspective and ii) assess technology- and policy-based approaches to shifting and improving energy use in the sector over time. [The Final Project Report is also available for further reading.](#) Contact: Oliver Broad – o.broad@ucl.ac.uk